

Digital
Humanities
& Heritage

1st DARIAH-HR International Conference,
Zadar, Croatia / **13 - 15 October 2021**

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Digital Humanities & Heritage

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Editors

Koraljka Kuzman Šlogar, Anamarija Žugić Borić

Proofreading

Jelena Vincelj

Layout

Zrinka Denić

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Zrinka Denić

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Digital Humanities & Heritage

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University of Zadar, Rectorate

13-15 October 2021

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PROGRAM

Day One: 13/10/2021

9:30 - 17:00 Pre-Conference Workshop / SSHOC & ELDAH: Data Protection in Research Practice: The GDPR and the ELDAH Consent Form Wizard

Walter Scholger, Vanessa Hanneschläger, Paweł Kamocki,
Koraljka Kuzman Šlogar

Day Two: 14/10/2021

9:30 - 10:45 Opening Session

Welcome speech

Mirna Willer: Relevance of 'Cultural Information' for Digital Humanities
(Reflections on the Ideas Behind Seminars "Archives, Libraries, Museums:
Possibilities for Co-operation Within the Environment of the Global
Information Infrastructure")

Anna Maria Tamaro: Intersection of Digital Humanities and Digital
Library

10:45 - 11:15 COFFEE BREAK

11:15 - 12:45 Session 02: Digital Humanities & Open Science

Session Chair: Koraljka Kuzman Šlogar

Jennifer Edmond: The Arts and Humanities: From Tourists to Citizens in
the Republic of Data

Jadranka Stojanovski: From Concepts, Elements and Principles to
Practices and Standards of Open Science

Ivan Marić: Croatian Open Science Cloud Initiative - HR-OOZ

Discussion

12:45 - 14:00 LUNCH BREAK

14:00 - 15:30 Session 03: Cultural Heritage in Digital Humanities

Session Chair: Anne Gilliland

Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra: When Open Data Starts With a Handshake: The
Heritage Data Reuse Charter

Shangyun Shen: The Joint Programming Initiative Cultural Heritage and
Global Change

Cécile Chantraine Brailon, Laurence Delbarre-Willard: Playing in a
Traditional Venue vs. Playing in a Non-traditional Venue: Measuring
Performance

Discussion

15:30 - 16:00 COFFEE BREAK

16:00 - 17:00 Session 04: Posters & Projects

Session Chair: Marijana Tomić

Benedikt Perak: The Use of Natural Language Processing Tools and
Resources in Digital Humanities

Karl Heinz: ICARUS - More Than Just a Network

Anamarija Žugić Borić: Working Group Theatralia

Drahomira Cupar: Tezaurus.hr

Day Three 15/10/2021

9:30 - 11:00 Session 05: Digital Methods and Tools

Session Chair: Tihomir Živić

Marko Tadić: Current Pan-European Language Technologies Initiatives:
An Opportunity for Low-Resourced Languages

Achim Rabus: AI-Assisted Transcription of Glagolitic Sources Using
Transkribus

Antoine Doucet, Axel Jean-Caurant: The NewsEye Approach to Historical
Newspapers

Discussion

11:00 - 11:15 COFFEE BREAK

11:15 - 12:45 Session 06: Information Organization for the Digital Humanities

Session Chair: Mirna Willer

Koraljka Golub: Information and Knowledge Organisation in Digital
Humanities

Ana Vukadin: Metadata Standards and Digital Humanities: The Example of the KAM Cataloguing

Walter Scholger: Communicating Digital Heritage: Ethical and Legal Barriers - And Some Ways to Overcome Them - To Open Access

Discussion

12:45 – 14:00 LUNCH BREAK

14:00 - 15:30 Session 07: Digital Infrastructures

Session Chair: Ivan Marić

Edward Gray: DARIAH ERIC: Empowering Arts and Humanities Research on a National and International Level

Marko Tadić: Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN-ERIC)

Šime Smolić: The Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE-ERIC)

Marijana Glavica: Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA-ERIC / CROSSDA)

Dragan Bagić, Luka Jurković, Jelena Ostojić: European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS-ERIC)

Discussion

15:30 - 15:45 CLOSING SESSION

15:45 - 16:00 COFFEE BREAK

16:00 - 17:00 Session 08: Posters & Projects

Session Chair: Vlatka Lemić

Maurizio Toscano, Lidia Bocanegra Barbecho, Salvador Ros Muñoz, Elena González-Blanco: Insights on Scholarly Primitives From Digital Humanities Research in Spain

Alba Irollo: Bringing Digital Cultural Heritage to Digital Humanities

Caroline Maximoff: Time Machine – On the Way to the 'Big Data of the Past'

Marijana Tomić, Laura Grzunov: Citizen Science in Croatian Glagolitism

ABSTRACTS

European Social Survey in Croatia: Past, Present and Future Developments

Dragan Bagić

ESS-ERIC National Coordinator for Croatia
University of Zagreb
dbagic@ffzg.hr

Luka Jurković

Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences
University of Zagreb
ljurkovi@ffzg.hr

Jelena Ostojić

Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences
University of Zagreb
jostojic@ffzg.hr

Authors will present developments of Croatian participation in the European Social Survey ([European Social Survey](#) | [European Social Survey \(ESS\)](#)). The European Social Survey (ESS) is an academically driven cross-national survey that has been conducted across Europe since its establishment in 2001. Every two years, face-to-face interviews are conducted with newly selected, cross-sectional samples. The survey measures the attitudes, beliefs and behaviour patterns of diverse populations in more than thirty nations. In 2013, ESS was awarded ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) status.

For the first time, Croatia joined ESS in rounds 4 (2008) and 5 (2010), but it missed the three next waves. Authors will present circumstances in which Croatia returned to ESS in round 9, now with the status of a full member country of ESS-ERIC, the model of financing and organization of team and main research activity. In the presentation, special attention will be dedicated to plans for future developments, both for the promotion of usage of data among researchers and policy-related usage of data.

Insights on Scholarly Primitives From Digital Humanities Research in Spain

Maurizio Toscano

The Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT)
maurizio@ugr.es

Salvador Ros Muñoz

The UNED Digital Humanities Laboratory (LINHD)
sros@scc.uned.es

Lidia Bocanegra Barbecho

University of Granada (UGR)
lbocanegra@go.ugr.es

Elena González-Blanco

The Center for the Governance of Change (IE University)
egonzalezblanco@faculty.ie.edu

This poster has been awarded with the Best Poster Award at the DARIAH2020 virtual annual event ([DARIAH-EU Twitter: Best Poster Award](#)).

In order to provide the global community of scholars working in this field with a greater understanding of the current Spanish scenario, LINHD has recently promoted a research on the evolution of Digital Humanities in Spain in the last 25 years, a timeframe comparable with Unsworth's first formulation of scholarly primitives.

More than 1,000 records have been mapped, distributed as follow: 577 researchers; 368 projects; 88 resources; 9 post-graduate courses; and 8 specialised journals. Digital resources (i.e. repositories of documents, collections of artefacts, crowdsourcing platforms, dictionaries, databases, etc.), which are the object of this poster, have been produced, most of the time, with the aim to publish a service to improve the basic of day-to-day research workflow in the Humanities.

Our initial objectives were:

- to classify and describe the digital resources mapped according with the classical and new scholarly primitives, in order to highlight presences, absence and recurring associations of these categories
- to visualize the relationships between scholarly primitives and other dimensions in our data, like discipline and typology
- to identify how the introduction of digital tools and methods has affected the basic functions of research in the Humanities in Spain over time.

Data analysed is part of a larger dataset that can be downloaded at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3893546>.

The whole dataset has been extensively analysed in [Digital humanities in Spain: Historical perspective and current scenario](#).

BIOGRAPHIES

DRAGAN BAGIĆ

Dragan Bagić is Associate Professor at the Department of Sociology, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Zagreb. His research interests include political sociology, industrial relations, sociology of migration and social research methodology. He has more than 20 years of experience in survey-based social research, both scientific and applied. In 2019, he was named the first national coordinator of ESS-ERIC ([European Social Survey | European Social Survey \(ESS\)](#)) for Croatia. He was also one of the initiators of the establishment of the Croatian Social Science Data Archive ([CROSSDA – Croatian Social Science Data Archive](#)). Currently he is serving as vice-dean for research and international cooperation.

LIDIA BOCANEGRA BARBECHO

PhD in History (2006), University of Lleida and Master in European Project Design (2018) at Venice International University. Senior researcher with a Tenure Track position at Contemporary History Department at University of Granada. Digital Humanities, Digital Culture and Citizen Science specialist with main focus on crowdsourcing projects, current history and migration studies. Currently, L. Bocanegra is PI of three ongoing research projects: *Co-History - Analysis of Public Participation in Historical Research From the Perspective of Citizen Science* ([cohistoria.es](#)), funded by the Junta de Andalucía (FEDER); *Crowdsourcing in History. New Participatory and Inclusive Methodological Challenges in Historical Research in Spain*, funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (MICINN); and *e-xiliad@s Project* ([e-xiliad@s](#)), funded twice by the Spanish Ministry of Labour and Immigration. Since 2015, Lidia is responsible for the Digital Humanities area through the Medialab UGR (Laboratory of Research in Culture and Digital Society) at the University of Granada; she is also an expert evaluator for the European Commission, through the Research Executive Agency (2015, 2020).

Lidia has carried out research stays in Italy, Argentina (PhD Grants), Ireland, Cuba and Colombia (postdoctoral grants). During her postdoctoral period, she researched and worked (2007-2012) at ICT multinationals companies in Cork-Ireland (Trend Micro, VoxPro Group/Google); whose technological expertise she adapted and applied, by way of knowledge transfer, to HD research projects. In 2020, Lidia has been awarded with the prize for the *Best participation/presence in social media* with the project

e-xiliad@s, through the prestigious Association of Hispanic Digital Humanities (2020); she was also awarded by the Best Poster: *Insights on Scholarly Primitives From Digital Humanities Research in Spain* by the DARIAH Annual Event 2020: Scholarly Primitives. L. Bocanegra is the author, co-author and editor of about forty scientific publications, the vast majority in high-impact publications and scientific journals.

CÉCILE CHANTRAINE BRAILLON

Cécile Chantraine Brailon has been a university professor in Hispanic Studies at La Rochelle University since 2018 and her research focuses on Hispanic-American theatre and performing arts. After having conducted a line of research as part of the ANR CHispa project (2014-2017 / Project leader: Fatiha Idmhand) on the scientific exploitation of writers' archives through digital technology, she is currently working on several complementary programmes on the computerisation of research in the Performing Arts: the VISUAL STAGING programme (CPER MAuVE 2019-2022 with Carole Viñals), the e-spect@teur project at the University of La Rochelle (ACI JCJC, 2020) and the ESNA regional project (École du Spectateur de Nouvelle Aquitaine, 2021-24). She is also leading a work package in the Erasmus+ Partnership DiMPA project (Digital Methods Platform for Arts and Humanities / 2020-2023). Her current research interests aim to contribute to the theorization of the analysis of the performing arts: to this end, she also focuses her work on the design of digital tools offering specific functionalities for research in this field, concerning not only preservation (conservation of the creative process and performance), but also the analysis of performing arts data (genetic criticism, semiology, cultural analysis).

DRAHOMIRA CUPAR

Drahomira Cupar, PhD, is an assistant professor at the University of Zadar, Department of Information Sciences, Croatia. She obtained her PhD in Information Sciences in 2013. She is currently working at the Department of Information Sciences at the University of Zadar and teaching undergraduate and graduate courses in scholarly communication and academic writing, classification and subject indexing, and sociology of reading. She served as the President of the Croatian Reading Association (CroRA) ([Hrvatsko čitateljsko društvo](#)) (2012-2014). She is a member of the following professional organizations: Croatian Library Association (CLA) ([Croatian Library](#)

[Association](#)) (president of the Committee for classification and subject indexing), CroRA, ISKO (International Society for Knowledge Organization) ([International Society for Knowledge Organization: ISKO](#)), IFLA (Information Coordinator for Subject Analysis and Access Section) (<https://www.ifla.org/>). She was involved in the organization of several conferences and events organized by the Department (LIDA, PubMet, BOBCATSSS and summer schools) and is a co-director for the biennial international conference Libraries in the Digital Age (LIDA). She is a recipient of the CLA award Eva Verona which is presented to the best young LIS professionals (2012). She participates in the European project OPERAS-P ([OPERAS-P](#)) and TRIPLE ([Triple – Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration](#)). She is a coordinator of the DARIAH-HR project Tezaurus.hr.

LAURENCE DELBARRE WILLARD

Laurence Delbarre Willard is an engineer in instrumentation and experimental techniques at the SCALAB research laboratory and technical manager at EquipEx IrDIVE. She first worked as a Technical Manager Engineer for experimental physics at the Université du Littoral Côte d'Opale, then joined the University of Lille in 2012 for the acquisition of the IrDIVE platform's equipment, its installation and commissioning, and today contributes to the implementation and support of research projects with the various laboratories and partners using IrDIVE equipment. She participates in training on the implementation of experimental devices and their use for researchers and students (oculometry, recording of physiological parameters, kinematics, behavioural analysis: PPNESA European Master students). Her achievements include the 3D digitisation of sculptures ("La petite Châtelaine" C. Claudel, Musée de la Piscine Roubaix for Inventit, Oct.2014, and the Dubut vase "Persée délivrant Andromède", Palais des Beaux-arts de Lille, May 2015), capturing the singer's gestures with motion capture at A. Petit's show (Fresnoy, January 2015), etc.

ANTOINE DOUCET

Antoine Doucet is a tenured full Professor in computer science at the L3i laboratory of the La Rochelle University since 2014. At La Rochelle, he leads the research group in document analysis, digital contents and images (about 50 people) and directs the ICT department of the Vietnam-France University of Science and Technology of Hanoi. In addition, he is the coordinator of the H2020 project NewsEye ([NewsEye: NewsEye](#)), running until 2022, focusing on augmenting access to historical newspapers across domains and languages. He further leads the effort on semantic enrichment for low-resourced languages in the context of the H2020 project Embeddia ([EMBEDDIA – Cross-Lingual Embeddings for Less-Represented Languages in European News Media](#)). His main research interests lie in the fields of information retrieval, natural language processing, (text) data mining and artificial intelligence. The central focus of his work is the development of methods that scale to very large document collections and that use as few external resources as possible, in order to be particularly applicable to documents of any type written in any language, from news articles to social networks, and from digitized manuscripts to digitally-born documents. Antoine Doucet holds a PhD in computer science from the University in Helsinki (Finland) since 2005, and a French research supervision habilitation (HDR) since 2012.

JENNIFER EDMOND

Jennifer Edmond is Associate Professor of Trinity College Dublin, co-director of the Trinity Center for Digital Humanities and Director of Trinity's MPhil in Digital Humanities and Culture. Jennifer also serves as President of the Board of Directors of the pan-European research infrastructure for the arts and humanities, DARIAH-EU ([DARIAH | Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities](#)). She represents this body on the Open Science Policy Platform (OSPP), which supports the European Commission in developing and promoting Open Science policies. Until 2016, Jennifer coordinated the €6.5m CENDARI FP7 (2012-1026) project and is a partner in the related infrastructure cluster, PARTHENOS ([PARTHENOS Project – Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies](#)). She was also coordinator of the 2017-2018 ICT programme-funded project KPLEX ([KPLEX project](#)), which investigated bias in big data research from a humanities perspective, and is currently a partner on the CHIST-ERA project PROVIDE-DH ([Providedh – PROgressive Visual DEcision-Making in Digital Humanities](#)), which is investigating progressive visualisation as a support for managing uncertainty in humanities research.

MARIJANA GLAVICA

Marijana Glavica works at the library of the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Zagreb, where she is responsible for the implementation, development and maintenance of library information systems. She also teaches information literacy to psychology students. In recent years, her main interests are in the area of research data management in social sciences, particularly publishing and archiving research data. She has been involved in several international projects in cooperation with the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives ([CESSDA](#)) and its service providers, through which she worked on the establishment of the Croatian Data Archive and Services for the Social Sciences. Currently, she is representing Croatia in the CESSDA ERIC Service Providers' Forum.

KORALJKA GOLUB

Koraljka Golub is the head of the iSchool at Linnaeus University, [Information Institute \(iInstitute\) | Inu.se](#). She is also co-leading a Digital Humanities Initiative at Linnaeus University ([Research in Digital Humanities | Inu.se](#)). Her core research is in the field of digital libraries and information retrieval, with particular focus on topics related to knowledge organization, integrating existing knowledge organization systems with social tagging and/or automated subject indexing, and evaluating resulting end-user information retrieval.

Three of her major research projects from the past are:

EASTER ([EASTER | Project Home Page](#)) which dealt with the evaluation of algorithms for automated subject classification and indexing in the context of information retrieval

EnTag ([Enhanced Tagging for Discovery \(EnTag\) | Home Page](#)), on the potential of combining social tagging with Dewey Decimal Classification and Library of Congress Subject Headings

TRSS ([Terminology Registry Scoping Study | Home Page](#)), a scoping study of terminology registries for UK's further and higher education needs.

She works as an associate professor at the Department of Library and Information Science, School of Cultural Sciences, Linnaeus University ([Linnéuniversitetet | Inu.se](#)). She also serves as an adjunct at the School of Information Studies, Charles Sturt

University (School of Information and Communication Studies), Australia. For over five years in the recent past she worked as an information science researcher at UKOLN, University of Bath (UKOLN), United Kingdom.

Her educational background covers technology, social sciences and humanities. In 2007 she obtained her doctoral degree from the Department of Information Technology, Lund University (Lund University), Sweden, on the topic of automated subject classification. Her earlier degrees are from the Department of Information Sciences and the Department of English, University of Zagreb (UniZG), Croatia.

ELENA GONZÁLEZ BLANCO

Elena González Blanco is the Research Director of “LyrAlcs”, an AI and TL project at the Center for the Governance of Change at IE University and a professor of Artificial Intelligence applied to business at the IE University School of Technology. Likewise, she is the Global Head of Digital for Wealth Management and Insurance of Santander and was General Manager of Europe at the insurtech startup Coverwallet. She is an expert in Digital Transformation and Innovation, a specialist in the field of linguistic technology and has been responsible for Product Development in Artificial Intelligence at Minsait-Indra. She is also an internationally renowned researcher, and led POSTDATA, the ERC excellence European research project on linguistic technology and the semantic web.

She was the director and founder of the first Laboratory for Innovation in Digital Humanities in Spain: www.linhd.uned.es, and is also a member of numerous international committees (member of the Scientific Advisory Board of the largest European research infrastructure for linguistic technology CLARIN and advisor of the Venture Capital Related).

She is a doctor and has been a teacher and researcher at Harvard University, King's College, UNAM and Bonn. She was ranked number #1 in 2018 and #3 in 2019 in the Choiseul Ranking *Economic Leaders of the Future of Spain* (www.choiseul.es). She has been selected as one of the Top 100 women in Spain in the 2016, 2017 and 2018 editions of the www.lastop100.es contest and awarded the Julián Marías 2017 research award in the under-40 category.

EDWARD J. GRAY

Edward J. Gray is the Research Infrastructure Coordinator at the TGIR Huma-Num (CNRS) and the Officer for National Coordination at DARIAH ERIC, the European Research Infrastructure for the Digital Arts and Humanities. He leads the Curation Task Force in the SSHOC Project, which is developing the SSH Open Marketplace, a discovery platform for digital humanities tools and services. He earned his doctorate in history from Purdue University, where his dissertation, “The Marillac: Family Strategy, Religion, and Diplomacy in the Making of the French State during the Sixteenth and Seventeenth Centuries”, examined the ways in which familial politics impacted the formation of the early modern French state. His dissertation research has been funded by a bourse Chateaubriand from the French Embassy in the United States, a Vincentian Studies Institute Grant from DePaul University, and a Purdue Research Foundation Grant from Purdue University. While a *doctorant invité* at the École nationale des chartes in Paris, he earned a master's degree in Technologies numériques appliquées à l'histoire (TNAH), where he is also *chargé de cours*. Before working at Huma-Num, Edward was the Digital Humanities Coordinator at the Maison Européenne des Sciences de l'Homme et de la Société in Lille. In addition to early modern religion and politics and the digital humanities, he is also interested in interrogating the periodization of the ‘medieval’ and ‘early modern’, and exploring global approaches to early modern history. He received an M.A. in History from Purdue University in 2015 and a B.A. in History and French from the University of Alabama in 2013.

LAURA GRZUNOV

Laura Grzunov works as a research assistant at the Department of Information Sciences at the University of Zadar. She teaches seminars and exercises in the courses Digital Humanities, Information Organization, Theory and Practice of Information Organization, Processing of Old and Rare Materials, Evaluation of information services and Information Collection Management. Since 2017, she has been an associate on the university project *Digitization, Bibliographic Description and Research of Texts Written on Glagolitic, Croatian Cyrillic and Latin Scripts Until the End Of 19th Century in Zadar and Šibenik Area* which is being carried out at the University of Zadar by Centre for Research in Glagolism. She is also one of the collaborators on the scientific project *Civil Science In the Field of Glagolitics: from crowdsourcing to knowledge*

which is implemented at the Center for Research in Glagolism at the University of Zadar and within the activities of DARIAH-HR digital research infrastructure.

VANESSA HANNESSCHLÄGER

Vanessa Hanneschläger is a digital humanist and German literature scholar. She obtained her PhD from the University of Vienna and worked as a researcher at the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH) of the Austrian Academy of Sciences and is currently doing her postdoc at the German Literature Archive. She is co-chair of the DARIAH working group ELDAH ([ELDAH – Ethics and Legality in the Digital Arts and Humanities – a working group of DARIAH-EU](#)), vice-chair of the CLARIN Legal and Ethical Issues Committee ([CLIC](#)), and the lead of the DARIAH ELDAH Consent Form Wizard project. Vanessa is actively pursuing Open Science. She was a Wikimedia Germany Open Science Fellow in 2017/18, and won the Open Minds Award in 2017. She is a member of the Open Science Network Austria (OANA) and teaches Digital Humanities / Open Science at the University of Vienna.

KARL HEINZ

After the studies of history, tibetology and the Czech and Hungarian language, acquisition of the academic degree Magister at the University of Vienna in December 1995. Subsequently attendance and completion of the training course at the Institute for Austrian Historical Research for archival science and historical auxiliary science and acquisition of the academic degree Master of Advanced Studies (MAS) in September 1995. In June 2004, completion of doctoral studies (History) in June 2004.

From 1995 onwards, freelance historian especially in the research fields of Lower Austrian local history, diplomatic and palaeographic research, Austro-Hungarian relationship and humanism in East-Central Europe. For two years from 2000, management of the *Netzwerk Geschichte* association with a focus on job placement within the history department. From 2003, coordinator of the Monasterium platform ([Monasterium.net | ICARUS](#)) and from 2008, co-founder of ICARUS – International Centre for Archival Research ([ICARUS | International Centre for Archival Research](#)) and General manager of ICARUS.

Various publications and lectures regarding digitization and online presentation

of primary sources. Participation in organizing the online resources Monasterium, Matricula ([Matricula | ICARUS](#)) and Topothek ([Topothek Portal – Das lokale Online-Archiv](#)), and collaboration in various European projects, such as ENArC, Co:op, Time Machine and European Digital Treasures.

ALBA IROLLO

Dr. Alba Irollo is in charge of Europeana Research at the Europeana Foundation ([Europeana Foundation](#)), The Hague, which oversees Europeana, the European Commission's initiative for Digital Cultural Heritage. Europeana Research's area embraces the interconnections between Digital Cultural Heritage and the so-called Digital Humanities. In particular, Dr. Irollo oversees research projects, partnerships and collaborations with universities, research institutions and infrastructures, as well as cultural heritage institutions engaged in improving their digital collections for research purposes. She represents Europeana at DARIAH and LIBER. She supervises the Europeana Research Grants Programme and together with the board chair, coordinates the activity of the Europeana Research Advisory Board. She also leads the Europeana Research Community. Before joining the EF, she spent a period of time at the European Commission itself in Brussels. In the Cabinet of the European Commissioner for Education, Culture, Youth and Sport, she gained wide-ranging experience in the field of cultural policy. Inter alia, she worked on the preparatory phase of the European Year of Cultural Heritage (2018). She holds a PhD in History of Art and, besides being busy with cultural policy, is an active researcher in the fields of History of Collecting and Heritage/Museum Studies.

AXEL JEAN-CAURANT

Dr. Axel Jean-Caurant is a research engineer at the L3i laboratory of the University of La Rochelle University. He obtained his PhD in computer science in 2018 and his thesis was on the accessibility of documents inside digital libraries. The focus of his work was put on two distinct aspects. The first is to understand how researchers are using these online platforms and how to train them to understand the changes data has undergone during the digitisation processes. The second is the study of the impact of the quality of documents on accessibility. Axel is now working full time on the NewsEye project ([NewsEye: NewsEye](#)) and is in charge of developing a demonstrator which will hold the data the project researchers are interested in, along with the different tools developed during the project.

LUKA JURKOVIĆ

Luka Jurković is an assistant and a doctoral student at the Department of Sociology, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Zagreb, where he received his master's degree in 2019. He is currently a teaching assistant on several courses in classical social theory, as well as statistics and research methodology in the social sciences. Since June 2020 he is a member of the Croatian national team of the European Social Survey (ESS) where he is responsible for preparing the national questionnaire and sample design, as well as conducting data collection and data processing. Prior to joining Croatia's national ESS ERIC team, he worked as a research assistant for a market research company, where he was responsible for the setup, preparation, and implementation of market and public opinion research projects. In his brief time as an assistant at the Department of Sociology, he has published four papers in peer-reviewed academic journals and has participated in several national and international academic conferences. His major research interests include sociology of health, work-life balance, sociology of sexuality, and quantitative research methodology.

PAWEŁ KAMOCKI

As a lawyer and linguist, Paweł Kamocki, currently at the Institute for German Language in Mannheim, combines expertise in the areas of IT law, intellectual property, data protection and corpus linguistics. His interests include open innovation, privacy by design and by default, and research data management. He is the head of the CLARIN Legal Issues Committee (<https://www.clarin.eu/governance/legal-issues-committee>), has worked for many years in various working groups on legal issues in digital research, and has produced a large number of relevant publications and presentations in this area.

KORALJKA KUZMAN ŠLOGAR

Koraljka Kuzman Šlogar acquired her MA degree in history, ethnology and museology and subsequently PhD in ethnology and cultural anthropology at the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Zagreb. Since 2001, she has been employed at the Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Research in Zagreb and, as head of the Department of Documentation, has been working on the planning and management

of different digitization projects and the creation and development of a digital repository of intangible cultural heritage. She has been involved in the projects of publishing archival material, making ethnographic documentary films and creation of virtual and museum exhibitions. Simultaneously, she has been working on scientific projects in the fields of digital humanities and cultural anthropology, she participates in national and international conferences and is the author of numerous scientific and professional papers.

Currently the focus of her interest is the development of the e-infrastructure for the arts and humanities, work on the development of the functionality of digital platform and repository and linking with similar institutions at national and international level in order to create a virtual scientific-research network. She is a national coordinator for Croatia at DARIAH-ERIC ([DARIAH-HR](#)) and co-chair of the DARIAH-EU Working group on Ethics and Legality in the Digital Arts and Humanities ([Ethics and Legality in the Digital Arts and Humanities \(ELDAH\)](#)). She is a member of different national and pan-European working groups and several committees.

IVAN MARIĆ

Ivan Marić is the Director of the University of Zagreb University Computing Centre SRCE, where he began his career in 1990. During his time in SRCE, he played an important role in the creation and construction of the Croatian academic and research network at the beginning of 1990's, and has since then participated in numerous national initiatives related to building Croatian e-infrastructure. Currently, he leads the national strategic project Croatian Scientific and Educational Cloud (HR-ZOO) ([HR-ZOO | Srce](#)), which aims to build a new generation of e-infrastructure for advanced science and modern education, and is the president of the Council of the Croatian Open Science Cloud initiative (HR-OOZ).

On the international level, he is actively involved in building and governing major pan-European e-infrastructures like GEANT and EGI. Mr. Marić holds several positions in international organizations as the national representative for Croatia – he is an official Croatian delegate in the EOSC Steering Board and the EOSC Association General Assembly. He has been the Croatian representative in the Future Internet Forum (FIF) from 2016, and an e-IRG delegate from 2006. He is also the Croatian representative in the Horizon Europe Research Infrastructure Programme Committee.

CAROLINE MAXIMOFF

Caroline Maximoff is an administrative and communication/dissemination expert working internationally, based in Vienna, Austria. Born on 30 September 1980 in Germany to Austrian and Russian-Italian descended parents, the family moved back to Austria early on, where Caroline finished primary school and secondary humanistic education (modern language branch) in 1998. After three years of studying architecture at the Technical University of Graz/AT, she moved to Vienna to continue to study History of Art at the University of Vienna/AT.

From September 2005 to August 2006, Caroline attended an ERASMUS year-abroad at the University College Dublin/IE, enrolling in history, art, and archaeology classes.

In 2008, Caroline began working for the recently founded archival association ICARUS – International Centre for Archival Research ([International Centre for Archival Research: ICARUS](#)) taking over various tasks from general administration, community management, communication and dissemination to more specific project and financial management of several EU-funded projects.

In May 2011, she took over the administration and project management position for the project ENArC ([ENArC | European Network on Archival Cooperation](#) ENArC | [European Network on Archival Cooperation](#)) in the St. Pölten Episcopal Archives and supporting the application of the project MEN & BOOKS until her maternity leave in December 2012 (until October 2014). Carrying on the administrative, financial and project management duties for the project co:op ([co:op – the creative archives' and users' network](#)) until her second maternity leave starting in April 2015, Caroline left the St. Pölten archives and started working again for ICARUS in September 2016.

Since March 2020, Caroline is part of the core staff of the Time Machine Organisation ([Time Machine Organisation](#)) being in charge of the financial administration and community management. In May 2020, she took over the additional role of Chief Communication Officer during the maternity leave of Ms Kerstin Muff.

JELENA OSTOJIĆ

Jelena Ostojić is an assistant and doctoral student at the Department of Sociology, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Zagreb. She previously worked at the Study of Social Work, the Department of Social Policy and in the Department of Analytics and

Research of the Croatian Employment Service. She participates in several research projects whose thematic backbones are industrial relations, precariousness in the labor market, and working conditions of temporary employees. She is a member of the Croatian national team of the European Social Survey.

BENEDIKT PERAK

Benedikt Perak, PhD philologist, corpus linguist, data scientist, is employed as an assistant professor at the The Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Rijeka, where he has been teaching courses in the field of linguistics, digital humanities and data science at the undergraduate and graduate level.

The main area of his research interest is related to the implementation and development of methods of digital humanities, natural language processing and data science in the field of social interaction and platforms for the development of digital assistants and advanced communication based on machine learning technologies and artificial intelligence.

He is the founder and head of the Laboratory for Research of Cultural Complexity at the Department of Cultural Studies ([Laboratorij za istraživanje kulturne složenosti | Cultural Complexity Lab - CULTURAL STUDIES](#)) as well as the Laboratory within a University Center for Artificial Intelligence and Cyber Security ([Centre for Artificial Intelligence and Cybersecurity – AIRI](#)), founded with the aim of establishing an infrastructure for conducting interdisciplinary scientific research of complex cultural phenomena in the interdisciplinary field of social sciences and humanities and support for the realization of scientific research projects in the real sector.

Benedikt is the leader and collaborator on several domestic and international projects and the author and curator of interactive projects related to the digitization of cultural heritage and the promotion of culture in tourism management. He is also the author of a number of scientific papers published in prestigious journals and a lecturer at numerous national and international conferences.

Finally, he is a member of numerous scientific consortia and professional institutions and organizations related to the development of digital systems.

A list of his papers can be found at [Pregled po CROSBi profilu: Benedikt Perak \(CROSBi Profil: 26656, MBZ: 324151\) - CROSBi](#).

ACHIM RABUS

Prof. Dr. Achim Rabus holds the Chair of Slavic Linguistics at the University of Freiburg, Germany. From 2013 until 2016, he was employed as a Professor at the University of Jena and the Aleksander Brückner Center for Polish studies at the Universities of Halle and Jena. Rabus defended his PhD thesis on the language of East Slavic spiritual songs in 2008 and his Habilitationsschrift on Slavic language contact in 2014. In 2012, he was awarded a Feodor Lynen fellowship to conduct research at the University of California, Berkeley, sponsored by the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation. From 2011 until 2016, he was a member of the Junior Academy Program of Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities. Since 2009, Rabus has been a member of the Special Commission on the Computer-Supported Processing of Mediæval Slavonic Manuscripts and Early Printed Books to the International Committee of Slavists, and since 2018, the President of the Commission.

He has been the principal investigator of several philological, sociolinguistics, and Digital Humanities projects. His current research focuses on Slavic sociolinguistics, dialectology, Handwritten Text Recognition, and (digital) historical linguistics.

SALVADOR ROS MUÑOZ

Salvador Ros is Director of the Laboratory of Innovation on Digital Humanities at UNED (Spanish Distance University), POSTDATA ERC, Starting Grant Technical PI at UNED and Module Convenor of Module V, devoted to innovation and technology in border security, and the European Master in Strategic Border Management. Salvador Ros has been Director of Learning Technologies at UNED for six years and Vice Dean of Technologies at the Computer Science School for six years. He has received the Extraordinary Doctoral Award at UNED for his PhD dissertation and two special best paper awards as well. He is an expert in strategic management and innovation in the public sector. He graduated in the Leadership Program for Public Sector Management from the IESE Business School, Universidad de Navarra, in Strategic University Senior Management from the Universidad de Nebrija y Politecnica de Barcelona, and in the Leadership Program for Innovation and Entrepreneurship in the Public Sector from the Deusto Business School, Universidad de Deusto.

He is a senior member of the IEEE Education Society since 2007. His research and professional activity, in general, is focused on enhanced learning technologies for distance learning scenarios and learning analytics, big data, and AI applied to science and humanities. He is also a strategic consultant for the public sector.

WALTER SCHOLGER

Walter Scholger studied History and Applied Cultural Sciences in Graz (Austria) and Maynooth (Ireland). He is the institute manager of the Centre for Information Modeling – Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities at the University of Graz (Austria). He is involved in several international projects focusing on the legal aspects of academia and digitization, a member (and co-lead) of several working groups of DH umbrella organizations dedicated to DH curricula development, digital publication and Open Science.

A veteran contributor to DARIAH-EU, he was one of the driving forces behind the DH Course Registry ([Digital Humanities Course Registry](#)) and has been active in several Working Groups, serving as Co-Lead of the Working Group on Ethics and Legality in Digital Arts and Humanities ([Ethics and Legality in the Digital Arts and Humanities \(ELDAH\)](#)) since 2017. In January 2019, he was appointed Deputy National Coordinator for DARIAH Austria and also serves as the speaker of the CLARIAH-AT consortium, the national association for Austrian contributions to the CLARIN and DARIAH ERICs.

SHANGYUN SHEN

Shangyun Shen works as a research specialist and communications manager at the secretariat of the JPI CH (European Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage [JPI CH](#)) in the Fondation des sciences du patrimoine, France. He is responsible for the administration of the initiative's online platform Heritage Research Hub and the social media linked to it. He also assists the preparation and launching of the transnational calls funded by the JPI CH.

Shangyun holds a joint master's degree on Sustainable Heritage Management from the KU Leuven, Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne, and the Padua University. He also has a second master's degree in Cultural and Religious Studies from the Hebrew University of Jerusalem. He has worked on several online publications focusing on the ICH of Egyptian Copts.

ŠIME SMOLIĆ

Šime Smolić is associate professor at the University of Zagreb, Faculty of Economics and Business (FEB) where he obtained his PhD in 2012. He has been the country team leader of the SHARE (*Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe*) ([The Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe \(SHARE\)](#)) study in Croatia since 2014 for the 4th consecutive wave, and a representative of the FEB – Scientific Partner Institution – in SHARE-ERIC. He has also been a researcher for the project *Health, Cultural, and Biological Determinants of Longevity: Anthropological Perspective on Survival in Very Old Age* (HeCuBa) from 2018. Since November 2020, he has been leading the work package 'Quality of healthcare' in the Horizon2020 project '*Non-intended Health, Economic and Social Effects of the Covid-19 Epidemic Control Decisions: lessons from SHARE (SHARE-COVID19)*' He has published more than twenty papers in peer-reviewed journals, and more than ten papers in conferences. His major research interests are health economics, economics of ageing, health economy and survey analysis. His teaching includes several courses: health economics, macroeconomics, economics of education and Croatian economy. He has been awarded for his teaching excellence in three academic years within the English taught undergraduate study programme at the FEB. During his career, he worked on several major projects: consultant – survey specialist for the World Bank survey on SMEs in Croatia (2018-2019), analysts in the project *Demographic Atlas of Croatian Medical Doctors* (2017, 2019, Croatian Medical Doctors Chamber), *In-Depth Analysis of the State Budget Expenditures of the Republic of Croatia* – chair of the *Health Care System Analysis* working group (2015, Croatian Ministry of finance and World Bank); contributor to the National Health Care Strategy 2012-2020 (2012, Croatian Ministry of Health). He is a reviewer for many international scientific journals, and a member of EAST (Central and Eastern European Ageing Societies) and ESRA (European Survey Research Organization). He speaks fluent English and Italian.

JADRANKA STOJANOVSKI

Jadranka Stojanovski is an Associate Professor at the University of Zadar and a research librarian at the Ruđer Bošković Institute with more than 20 years of professional experience in designing and creating scholarly information infrastructures, following open science principles. She has an interdisciplinary background in physics and information sciences gained during MSc studies in Physics and MA studies in Information Sciences

at the University of Zagreb. She also has a PhD in Information Sciences gained during studies in Information and Communication Sciences at the University of Zagreb. Her research is mainly in the areas of open science, scholarly communication, peer review, and research assessment.

She takes part in international communities, networks and projects concerning different aspects of open scholarly communication, including the Horizon 2020 projects NI4OS Europe, OPERAS-P Preparing Open Access in the European Research Area Through Scholarly Communication, TRIPLE Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration, and OpenAIRE Advancing Open Scholarship, TD COST Action TD1306 New Frontiers of Peer Review (PEERE) and CA COST Action CA15137 European Network for Research Evaluation in the Social Sciences and the Humanities (ENRESSH).

She is also a Croatian representative in the European Commission expert group on National Points of Reference on Scientific Information (E03477) and European Research Area and Innovation Committee (ERAC) Standing Working Group on Open Science and Innovation (SWG OSI).

MARKO TADIĆ

Marko Tadić,¹ linguist, full professor at the University of Zagreb, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Department of Linguistics. He has been the head of the Chair of Algebraic and Computational Linguistics at the same Department since 2001 and an associated member of the Croatian Academy of Sciences and Arts since 2008. He was also a member of the Standing Committee for the Humanities of the European Science Foundation (2009-2012) and a member of the National Council for the Humanities of the National Scientific Council of the Republic of Croatia (2004-2013, 2017-). His interests are in corpus linguistics, computational linguistics, language technologies and research infrastructures in (e-)humanities and social sciences. He published more than 80 papers and 5 books. He is also the co-author of the *Croatian Frequency Dictionary* (1999). He is also the (co)author of important language resources for

¹ Personal web page: http://www.ffzg.unizg.hr/oling/?page_id=88.
References in bib.irb.hr bibliographic base: <http://bib.irb.hr/lista-radova?autor=157043>.
Google Scholar: http://scholar.google.hr/citations?user=zpAvfFwAAAAJ&hl=en&citsig=AMstHGT-3v1t_0mYxWXngmNs1pkKZ_DqqNg.
ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-6325-820X>.
ResearchGate: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Marko_Tadic3.
Academia.edu: <https://ffzg.academia.edu/MarkoTadic>.

the Croatian language such as the *Croatian National Corpus* (hnk.ffzg.hr), *Croatian Morphological Lexicon* ([Hrvatski morfološki leksikon](http://Hrvatski_morfološki_leksikon)), *Croatian Dependency Treebank* ([Croatian Dependency Treebank - Zagreb](http://Croatian_Dependency_Treebank_-_Zagreb)) and the portal *Language Technologies for Croatian Language* (jthj.ffzg.hr). He was the leader of Croatian teams participating in several nationally funded projects as well as the FP7 RI project CLARIN ([CLARIN ERIC: Homepage](http://CLARIN_ERIC_Homepage)), FP7 project ACCURAT (www accurat-project.eu), ICT-PSP projects Let'sMT! ([Tilde MT](http://Tilde_MT)) and CESAR (w.w.cesar-project.net), FP7 project XLike ([HomePage - Linux Training](http://HomePage_-_Linux_Training)), the European Social Fund project HR4EU (HR4EU) and he is now leading the CEF projects MARCELL (<https://marcell-project.eu/>), EU Presidency Translator (hr.presidencymt.eu) and the Maria Skłodowska-Curie project CLEOPATRA (www.cleopatra-project.eu). He is the president and one of the founders of the Croatian Language Technologies Society.

ANNA MARIA TAMMARO

Anna Maria Tammaro has centered her research and teaching on digital library and digital heritage. Following the principle of putting the user community at the center, she has published the results of her research on the support of the digital library to the community and in particular to digital humanities scholars.

She obtained her PhD from the University of Northumbria with a thesis on the internationalization of LIS education for the digital library. She subsequently became involved in the design and teaching of joint courses between different universities.

She has been teaching in Parma since 2000 as a coordinator and lecturer of the International Information Studies Master (MAIS) with Northumbria University and subsequently (2006) of the International Master Digital Library Learning (DILL) with the University of Oslo, Tallinn and Parma. She has been a lecturer in the joint course of the Universities of Parma and Modena and Reggio since 2011, teaching digital publishing. Tammaro also dealt with open education and designed and taught (2016) the MOOC "Digital Library in Theory and Practice" on the European EMMA platform: the course in Italian, Spanish and English had 1500 participants.

Tammaro has coordinated and participated in numerous European projects on the digital library such as the most recent ROMOR, NMPLIS, NAVIGATE, OBERRED, concerning information literacy, gamification and research data management and NEWCOMER on community libraries.

Anna Maria Tammaro has been the Editor in Chief of the international journal *Digital library perspectives* (Emerald) since 2018.

She is active in international associations and is currently a member of the board of directors of ASIS & T and a member of AILIS. She was previously a member of the IFLA Governing Board (2007-2009; 2011-2013).

MARIJANA TOMIĆ

Dr. Marijana Tomić is Associate Professor and Head of the Department of Information Sciences, University of Zadar, Croatia, and Head of the Centre for Research in Glagoliticism. She teaches courses in the theory and practice of information organization, cataloguing of old and rare books, book history and digital humanities on undergraduate, graduate and postgraduate levels. She is a (co)supervisor of final and doctoral thesis. She is a member of the Section for the History of Books and Libraries of Croatian Library Association. She is a chair of the interdisciplinary scientific project *Digitization, Bibliographic Description and Research of Texts Written on Glagolitic, Croatian Cyrillic and Latin Scripts Until the End Of 19th Century in Zadar and Šibenik Area (Written heritage)* which is being carried out at the University of Zadar by the Department of Information Sciences in co-operation with the Vestigia Manuscript Research Centre of the University of Graz, Austria, and is available at the portals *Pisana baština* ([Pisana baština](http://Pisana_baština)) and *GлагоLab* (GлагоLab). She was involved in the five-year project *Production, Publishing and Maintaining National Cataloguing Rules: 2014-2018*. She is participating in a number of scientific projects, including *Linguistic, Paleographic and Codicological Analysis of Fragments of the Collection of Ivan Berčić of Zadar Provenance in Virtual Research Environment* (IP.01.2021.22) and *Protection of Zadar Cultural Heritage From the Negative Impact of Microorganisms* (IP-2021-01) and ERASMUS+ project *We Are All Together to Raise Awareness of Cultural Heritage* (WAAT). She is a recipient of the CLA award *Eva Verona* which is presented to the best young LIS professionals (2010), award for the best study of Croatian Renaissance heritage published in a scientific monograph (2014) and the University of Zadar Rector's Award (2019).

MAURIZIO TOSCANO

Maurizio Toscano is currently working at the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT) as the project leader of the H2020 BRIDGE2HE project and lead developer of two recently launched web platforms: Horizon Europe NCP Portal ([Horizon Europe NCP Portal: Home](#)) and Horizon Europe NCP Virtual Campus ([Horizon Europe NCP virtual campus](#)).

He has a PhD *cum laude* from the University of Granada, with a thesis on the design and implementation of Web Information Systems in History, Art History and Archaeology. He graduated in Cultural Heritage Conservation from Università degli Studi della Tuscia (Viterbo, Italy), with a thesis on architectural archaeology applied to early medieval churches, and has a master's degree in Information and Communication Technology in Archaeology from the Università di Siena, with a thesis on quantitative archaeology and spatial analysis.

In the last 8 years, he has been actively involved in drafting and executing several European, national and regional research projects. In the European context, from 2014 to 2017, he has been the project leader and technology manager for Eachtra Archaeological Projects Ltd. in the MEMOLA FP7 project ([MEMOLA Project MEditerranean MOUNTainous LANDscapes | an historical approach to cultural heritage based on traditional agrosystems](#)). Since then, he worked in three other H2020 projects: REACH, DESIR and INCULTUM. He is an expert evaluator for the European Commission for Cultural Heritage and for the Spanish Evaluation Agency (AEI) in the field of Digital Humanities. Since 2019, he has been a member of the Board of Directors of the international association for Hispanic Digital Humanities (HDH).

ERZSÉBET TÓTH-CZIFRA

Erzsébet works as the Open Science Officer of DARIAH-EU, where she is responsible for fostering and implementing policies and practices related to the open dissemination of research results in the humanities. Her advocacy activities include providing workshops, webinars and other training activities on a regular basis. She is also involved in European infrastructure-building projects such as OpenAire Advance ([advance](#)), OPERAS-P ([OPERAS-P](#)) and TRIPLE ([Triple – Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration](#)). She received her PhD in Cultural Linguistics and also has a background in scholarly communication.

ANA VUKADIN

Ana Vukadin works as a bibliographic standards and metadata officer in the National and University Library in Zagreb, Croatia. She is the current editor-in-chief of the *Rules for Description and Access to Resources in Libraries, Archives, and Museums* (KAM). Her areas of interest include bibliographic conceptual models, ontologies, authority control, controlled vocabularies, and semantic interoperability across the LAM community. She has authored the book *Metadata for Transmedia Resources* (Chandos, 2019), and has served as a member of several IFLA bodies, including the Cataloguing Section Standing Committee and the Bibliographic Conceptual Models Review Group.

MIRNA WILLER

Dr Mirna Willer retired as Full Professor at the Department of Information Sciences, University of Zadar, Croatia in 2018, where she taught from 2007. She taught courses in theory and practice of information organisation at the undergraduate, graduate and postgraduate levels. She worked from 1980 to 2007 as a systems librarian, standards officer and senior researcher at the National and University Library in Zagreb, Croatia, responsible for implementing IFLA UNIMARC bibliographic and authority formats in the Library's library management software, and for incorporating national cataloguing rules into the formats. She was responsible for the design and implementation of the Croatian Web Archive ([HAW](#)). She has been a member and chair of various national and international professional bodies. In 1997, in the capacity of Chair of the Professional Board of the Croatian Library Association she promoted the idea of investigating the possibility of co-operation between libraries, archives and museums. The seminar *Archives, Libraries, Museums: Possibilities of Co-operation within the Environment of the Global Information Infrastructure* dealt with the vision of this idea, theoretical framework from the aspect of information sciences, and ALM's standards aiming at the creation of the environment for the 'interoperability of content'. The seminars have been organized annually ever since. From 2013 to 2021, she served as Chair of the Professional Board for the project which resulted in the publication of the "Rules for description and access to resources in libraries, archives and museums".

She publishes widely. She wrote two books: *UNIMARC u teoriji i praksi* (*UNIMARC in Theory and Practice*) (1996) and *Bibliographic Information Organization in the Semantic Web* co-authored with Gordon Dunsire (2013).

ANAMARIJA ŽUGIĆ BORIĆ

Anamarija Žugić Borić¹ studied Comparative Literature and Latin Language and Literature at the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Zagreb, Croatia, where she is currently writing a PhD thesis on music as an aspect of dramaturgy in contemporary theater in Croatia. Prior to joining Croatia's National DARIAH Coordination Office in her capacity as an assistant, she worked as a TA at the Department of Classical Philology, University of Zagreb, and as an assistant in the Division of the History of Croatian Theater, Croatian Academy of Sciences and Arts. She also worked as a publishing house editor. Anamarija Žugić Borić is also a freelance music and theater critic, copywriter, copyeditor, and proofreader. She was engaged in various DH projects and workshops, in particular in the Open Philology Workshop in Leipzig, in the Croatiae auctores Latini (CroALa) collection and in the digitization of theatrical materials for the Digital Collection and Catalog of the Croatian Academy of Sciences and Arts. Her research interests include performing arts, digital theater, theatrical sound and music, archival processing, NLP, digital collections and digital editions. She is the Chair of the DARIAH-EU working group Theatralia, dedicated to exploring the possibilities of information and communications technology in the Performing Arts.

¹ ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2135-6343>.

CROSB: <https://www.bib.irb.hr/pregled/profil/111185>.

Academia.edu: <https://ffzg.academia.edu/Anamarija%C5%BDugi%C4%87>.

